

Adducts of *bis*-(2-Guanidinium Benzimidazole) Copper II Salts with Ammonia and Pyridine

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The four coordinated *bis*-(2-Guanidinium Benzimidazole) Copper II complexes change to hexa coordination when treated with ammonia gas. The resulting adducts have high magnetic moments (2.09 B.M.). In presence of pyridine the four coordinated copper complexes, however, could be converted to both penta and hexa coordinated adducts. The magnetic moments of pyridine adducts lie between 1.84—1.99 B.M. The electronic absorption spectra in pyridine show two wide peaks at 13.4 and 18.0 μ region, which support the octahedral structure. From the ratio $\sigma_{Cu}/\sigma_{Ni} = 1.28$ the structure is found to be moderately tetragonal.

The possibility that under certain conditions the coordination number of Copper (II) ion may be greater than four has been reported by many workers¹⁻⁴.

Under conditions of adequate magnetic dilution the cupric ion exhibits a moment somewhat above the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M., specially if the ligand distribution around it is octahedral. According to Figgis and Harris⁵ the effective moment is given by the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M., multiplied by the factor $1 + 2A/\Delta$, where Δ is the d_g-d_e separation in the octahedral crystalline field splitting and A the spin orbit coupling constant ($= 852 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). With $\Delta \sim 20,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, a moment of about 1.88 B.M. has been predicted by them for an octahedral copper complex.

The four coordinated *bis*-(2-Guanidinium Benzimidazole) Copper (II) complexes⁶ form adducts with ammonia gas and pyridine. In the present paper their preparation, properties and structures are discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bis-(2-Guanidinium Benzimidazole) Copper (II) chloride and sulphate were prepared⁶. The complexes are green in colour. Freshly prepared complexes were dissolved in just sufficient amount of pure pyridine when a brown solution was obtained. By allowing the solution to evaporate at the room temperature (27°), a sufficiently dry brown residue was obtained. This was kept in a desiccator charged with KOH and pyridine. On analysis the complex was found to be associated with three molecules of pyridine. It has a tendency to pyridine. The loss was found to take place in stages and the lower adducts could be isolated. The rate of loss of pyridine in air by the tri-pyridine adduct was highest, forming

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4. R. D. Gillard and G. Wilkinson, *ibid.*, 1963, 5885.
5. B. N. Figgis and C. M. Harris, *ibid.*, 1959, 585.
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the bi-pyridine adducts. The bi-pyridine adduct loses pyridine at a slower rate forming the mono-pyridine adducts. For about 2 gms of the *tris*-adduct, the *bis*-adduct is formed within half an hour in the air. The *bis*-adduct was found to be stable at a low temperature (below 10°). The mono pyridine adduct was stable for about 12 to 14 hr. at the room temperature (27°).

The ammonia adducts were formed by keeping the moist green four coordinated copper complexes in a desiccator charged with dry ammonia gas. After several days the complex chloride changed to brown and the complex sulphate into reddish brown. It was found that only the moist complexes formed the ammonia adducts readily. In case of ammonia only *bis*-adducts were formed. The ammonia adducts were more stable at the room temperature than the pyridine adducts. Analytical results of the compounds are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Compound	Cu	Found % anion	Py	Cu	Calculated % anion	Py
X Py ₃ Cl ₂	8.86	9.79	32.30	8.80	9.84	32.87
X Py ₃ SO ₄	8.44	12.80	31.80	8.50	12.86	31.74
X Py ₂ Cl ₂	9.96	11.31	24.01	9.88	11.05	24.54
X Py ₂ SO ₄	9.50	14.50	24.00	9.51	14.39	23.67
X Py Cl ₂	11.11	12.50	14.40	11.27	12.60	14.02
X Py SO ₄	10.60	16.21	13.64	10.79	16.31	13.42
X(NH ₃) ₂ Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	11.76	18.51	30.70*	11.83	12.59	31.30*
X(NH ₃) ₂ SO ₄ ·H ₂ O	11.12	17.00	29.90*	11.30	17.06	29.90*

X = Cu(C₅H₉N₃)₂

* is the percentage of nitrogen.

Magnetic susceptibility of the adducts were determined in a Guoy balance calibrated with Hg[Co(CNS)₄] at room temperature (300°K). For diamagnetic correction Pascal's values were used. Results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Compound	$\chi_M \times 10^6$	$\chi_M \times 10^6$	Dia. correc. $\times 10^6$	$\chi_A \times 10^6$	$\mu_B \cdot M.$
X Py ₃ Cl ₂	1.67	1204.9	392.17	1597.07	1.97
X Py ₃ SO ₄	1.61	1201.8	386.95	1588.81	1.96
X Py ₂ Cl ₂	2.00	1285.0	342.91	1627.91	1.99
X Py ₂ SO ₄	2.03	1355.0	337.69	1692.71	2.02
X Py Cl ₂	1.97	1109.9	293.65	1403.54	1.84
X Py SO ₄	1.90	1118.1	288.43	1406.58	1.84
X(NH ₃) ₂ Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	2.98	1598.77	253.61	1852.38	2.09
X(NH ₃) ₂ SO ₄ ·H ₂ O	2.84	1594.6	268.21	1862.81	2.09

X = Cu(C₅H₉N₃)₂.

Electronic absorption spectra of the *bis*-(2-Guanidinium Benzimidazole) Copper (II) chloride and sulphate in pyridine were taken in a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with one cm cell. The results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

X Cl ₂	13416 cm ⁻¹	15556 cm ⁻¹ (Shoulder)	18010 cm ⁻¹
X $\frac{1}{2}$ SO ₄	13605 cm ⁻¹	15431 cm ⁻¹ ..	18010 cm ⁻¹

X = Cu(C₆H₅N₃)₂.

Infra red spectra in nujol mull was taken in a Perkin-Elmer 521 spectrophotometer for diamine-*bis*-(2-Guanidinium Benzimidazole) Copper (II) chloride was sulphate; in both the cases a new band of medium intensity was found at 690 cm⁻¹ which was absent in *bis*-(2-Guanidinium Benzimidazole) Copper (II) chloride and sulphate.

DISCUSSION

From analytical results it is found that *bis*-(2-Guanidinium Benzimidazole) Copper (II) complexes form pyridine adducts with three, two and one molecule of pyridine. As the third molecule of pyridine is very quickly lost, it may be postulated not to be coordinated with the copper atom. The absorption spectra of the chloride and sulphate in pyridine show two peaks and a shoulder. The principal band for the chloride is 13416 cm⁻¹ whereas for the sulphate is 13604 cm⁻¹. From these Δ values, magnetic moments of 1.95 B.M. are expected for both the bi-pyridine adducts, which are very much in keeping with the experimental values (1.99 and 2.02 B.M.).

Jorgensen⁷ has defined a ratio $\sigma\text{Cu}/\sigma\text{Ni}$ between the wave number of the principal band of copper (II) complex, σCu and the wave number of the first spin allowed band of the octahedral nickel (II) complex, σNi with the same ligand. This ratio falls into three classes: (i) the highly tetragonal with $\sigma\text{Cu}/\sigma\text{Ni} = 1.6-1.8$, having only one absorption band, (ii) the complexes of six identical ligands with $\sigma\text{Cu}/\sigma\text{Ni} = 1.4$, having a shoulder at lower wave number; (iii) finally complexes of low tetragonality with $\sigma\text{Cu}/\sigma\text{Ni} = 1.1$, having two or three absorption bands. The last class of compounds are formed with special ligand like heterocyclic di-imines. The σNi of the chloride and sulphate has been found to be 10466 cm⁻¹. Taking 13416 cm⁻¹ and 13605 cm⁻¹ to be the principal bands for the copper (II) chloride and sulphate adducts, the ratio $\sigma\text{Cu}/\sigma\text{Ni} = 1.28$ in both the cases. Comparing with the reported values, it is suggested that these copper adducts are moderately tetragonal in structure. Though the constitution of the ligand present in the adducts are different, the donor atoms are all nitrogen, which may be the reason for the slightly low value of the ratio.

For the ammonia adducts, only the diamines could be definitely established. Because of the various -NH₂, = NH groups in the ligand it was not possible to obtain any information as to the coordination of the NH₃ groups from the antisymmetric and symmetric NH₃ stretchings. However, the NH₃ rocking vibration appeared as a new peak (690 cm⁻¹) in

7. C. K. Jorgensen, Absorption Spectra and Chemical Bonding in Complexes. Pergamon Press, 1962, p. 124.

the NH_3 adducts as compared with the four- coordinated complexes. In the adducts of *bis*-(2-Guanidinium Benzimidazole) Copper (II) sulphate, another sharp, medium intensity peak appeared at 826 cm^{-1} , which may be due to some crystal packing effects on the rocking vibration giving rise to another band there. The rocking frequency band supports that the ammonia molecules are coordinated to the metal⁸.

Bis-(2-Guanidinium Benzimidazole) Copper (II) complexes are all olive green in colour⁶. The green colour of the copper (II) complex is generally accepted as an indication of coordination greater than four. It is reasonable to say that in the present case four nitrogen atoms of the ligand coordinated to the copper ion lie in one plane, forming four coordinated square planar complex, with two water molecules in the axial position. These two water molecules are quite further from the metal atom than the other four nitrogen atoms, forming tetragonal structure. The ammonia and pyridine molecules, with higher donor property than water, displace the water molecule and are coordinated to the metal ions.

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8. K. Nakamoto, *Infrared Spectra of Inorganic Coordination Compounds*, 1963, John Wiley and Sons, p. 143.